

Unwrapping Forward-Looking Pipe Inspection Images into Rectangular Surface Maps for Defect Detection

Abstract

In our day-to-day life, we need a drainage infrastructure. However, the routine inspection of these infrastructures is hazardous, labor intensive, and irregular. A compact robot was built to inspect sewage pipelines. In this paper, surface maps are produced by converting imagery into a rectangular representation. These maps can be utilized to inspect pipelines for defects and debris. The process estimates the pipe center by identifying the darkest central region of the pipe and computing its centroid, then uses the center estimation to unwrap the pipe view into a rectangular panorama. The method is tested using open pipe-image datasets and calibrated on selected images. The pipeline is inspected by processing pipe imagery and evaluating whether the pipe geometry, center estimate, and image quality are suitable for unwrapping. Results show that the unwrapped map representation provides a coordinate system that makes the pipe surface easier to examine. This work demonstrates a low-cost, practical approach that can reduce inspection risk and help examine and document pipeline conditions. The center-detection algorithm achieved a mean Euclidean center error of 1.61 pixels across 100 GOOD-tier frames (97% within 10% tolerance), processes 640×640 images at 36.8 frames per second, and classification of 530 QV-Pipe videos showed that 24.5% of real-world sewer inspection footage is compatible with the current unwrapping method.

Keywords: Pipe inspection, drainage infrastructure, image processing, polar-to-Cartesian remapping, cylindrical unwrapping, surface mapping, defect detection, center detection, OpenCV, computer vision.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
BGR	Blue Green Red (OpenCV default color channel order)
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
OpenCV	Open Source Computer Vision Library
QV-Pipe	Quality Vision Pipe inspection video dataset

1 Introduction

Drainage and sewers are critical components of urban water infrastructure. They support public health, wastewater transport, and environmental protection, but over time they can develop defects such as cracks, blockages, corrosion, and joint failure. Many of these defects are only visible within pipes and are difficult to observe from the exterior; regular internal inspection is required to maintain pipeline infrastructure. In the United States, wastewater treatment facilities process approximately 34 billion gallons of wastewater a day. Furthermore, according to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), on average 14% of treated water is lost to leaks.¹

Earlier detection reduces infrastructure damage and repair costs by addressing defects before they escalate.^{2, 3} Some minor issues like small cracks, sediment buildup, corrosion and joint separation may occur, but with passing time these issues can expand into larger structural failures. And, if by mistake, the damage becomes severe, repair is unbearably expensive and also dangerous for labours.

There have been some local events which have showed the pressing need of pipe inspection. In December 2024, a sewer line broke near a pump station in Bay Point, Contra Costa County and it released a millions of gallons of untreated wastewater into nearby marshland. In this about a 20 million gallons were spilled, hurting the wildlife and destroying the environment. All this can occur due to hidden pipe damage. This example highlights the need for better drainage infrastructure inspection and maintenance.

Right now, sewer inspection relies on closed-circuit television (CCTV) and other inspection methods. To improve inspection in hazardous environments, researchers and engineers have begun to create a wide range of pipeline robotic systems. Cameras and sensors are usually mounted on these robots, capturing images and sensing various aspects of the internal surface of the pipe, allowing inspectors to examine conditions. This method makes inspection possible; however, the raw images are often difficult to interpret. Industry and government assessments show that sewer inspections and sewer maintenance are often dependent on the specific type of data collected, from recorded camera footage, defect observation, and sensor input. CCTV footages can be useful only if the pipeline damages can be seen and connected to the actual location of the pipe.^{4, 5, 6}

There will be a forward-facing inspection camera that will view the pipe as a circular tunnel. Due to this perspective of the camera, the pipe wall might appear curved around the centre of the image. In actuality, it should be a laid out flat surface. This illusion of perspective can

make it hard to analyse the sections of the pipe wall or follow large defects in multiple images captured. Features near the edge of the circular view may appear stretched, while features closer to the center may appear compressed or hidden by darkness. Inspectors must mentally interpret a three-dimensional cylindrical surface from a two-dimensional camera image. This process can be inconsistent because it depends on lighting, camera alignment, pipe material, worker experience, and image quality. Even if the camera is successfully recording the pipe interior, the final results depend on image quality, lighting, camera centering, and center estimation.

From the point of view of the robot, cracks and minor fissures along the inner surface can be hard to see and detect. Some current examples of pipeline robotic systems include Carnegie Mellon University’s Pipeline Explorer, a robot designed for long-range inspection of underground pipelines.^{7,8} However, while these systems can improve imagery and provide a live camera view of the passage, the forward-looking images collected can be hard to interpret directly because the inner wall appears in a circular form, making it hard to detect defects in the pipe.

This creates a need for image-processing methods that can make pipe imagery more readable. Current inspection footage is usually stored as a video, but videos do not usually provide a clear view of the pipe surface. This may cause inspectors to repeatedly pause and compare frames, which can make defect identification difficult. Instead of only viewing the original circular camera frame, the pipe wall can be converted into a rectangular representation. This does not completely remove all distortion, but it gives the inspector a more organized view of the pipe surface. A rectangular map can also make future automated defect detection easier because defects can be analysed in a more regularised and coordinated manner.

Therefore, image unwrapping is an important part of the pipe and borehole inspection strategies for deep research. The forward looking circular imagery can be turned into a rectangular panorama, easier to study as a map. In this paper, based on the cylindrical panorama approach of Deng et al.⁹ the center of a pipeline image is estimated and the circular view is unwrapped into a rectangular representation using OpenCV and NumPy. Similar pipe mapping concepts have been studied for sewer pipes and boreholes.^{10,11,12}

The basic idea of this project is to treat the inner surface of the pipe as a cylindrical surface. Seen from the front, each point on the visible wall can be described by how far away it is from the center of the pipe, and the angle around the pipe. This circular view can be unwrapped into a rectangular map in which the horizontal direction can be used to represent the angular position around the pipe and the vertical direction can be used to represent the radial distance from the centre. This provides a surface style view of the pipe wall which is easier to inspect than the original circular image. The aim of this paper is to construct a map for pipeline fault inspection.

2 Methods

The project used a compact robotic inspection system equipped with a camera to collect images from inside a pipe. The robot is designed to fit through the pipe and move forward and backward. The camera is positioned to capture images of the pipe interior along the robot’s direction of travel. The robot used an ESP32-S3-WROOM microcontroller with a

2 MP OV2640 camera module and can fit in pipes with diameters of 15 cm or larger. The net cost of the robot prototype hardware is approximately \$45. However, the main focus of this paper is the image-processing system rather than the robot itself. The quantitative image-processing evaluation in this paper was performed primarily on public QV-Pipe dataset frames rather than robot-collected field footage.

The system includes remote-control and sensing functions; however, this paper focuses on the image-processing used to transform the captured circular pipe views into flattened maps. Image processing is implemented in Python using OpenCV and NumPy. The image-processing workflow consisted of four major stages: image acquisition, preprocessing, center estimation, and cylindrical unwrapping. First, forward-looking pipe images were collected from the onboard camera or selected from the QV-Pipe dataset. Second, each frame was converted into grayscale and smoothed to reduce small lighting variations. Third, the center of the pipe was estimated using the darkest central region of the image. Finally, the circular pipe view was remapped into a rectangular surface representation. This structure made it possible to test out each part of the system and identify where errors occurred.

2.1 Image Acquisition

The imagery inputted into the image-processing system was acquired from the robot’s onboard camera or selected from the QV-Pipe dataset. The method is designed for forward-looking images in which the pipe appears as a circular tunnel with a dark central region. This assumes that the robot is inside the pipeline and is far enough from the exit that a dark centroid is visible. This assumption is important because the unwrapping process depends on estimating a center point. If the robot is tilted and is not parallel with the pipeline, if the pipe is only partially visible, or if water partially blocks the visibility of the pipe, the circular geometry is much harder to detect. These cases were useful for evaluating limitations, but were much less reliable at producing clean rectangular maps.

2.2 Preprocessing

Each image is converted to grayscale so that the center can be analyzed. The image was converted to grayscale because the center-detection process depends on brightness rather than color. In most forward-looking pipe images, the center of the pipe appears much darker than the surrounding wall. This is because less light reaches the far interior of the pipe, resulting in the color difference. This makes grayscale intensity a useful factor in identifying the pipe center. After converting the image to grayscale, a Gaussian blur with a 5×5 kernel was applied to make the image smoother and reduce image artifacts. Preprocessing was necessary as pipe images often contain shadows, low contrast, or uneven illumination. The Gaussian blur reduces the influence of random outliers, small stains, or artifacts that could lead to an inaccurate center estimation.

2.3 Center Estimation

The search for the pipe center was limited to a center region to avoid shadows and other not relevant parts of the background: The algorithm searches in this region over gray scale

thresholds to segment dark candidate regions that could correspond to the pipe center. The algorithm calculates the average grey value of different parts of the image and the area of each part.

This is one of the most important step for the center detection, because the estimated center is used in the unwrapping process. If the center is correct, the unwrapped map is very stable on the pipe wall. If the centre is off then one side of the pipe could be in tension and the other in compression. To avoid false detections of the center, the search is constrained to be within the central 70% of the width and height of the image. The above is based on the assumption that the robot viewing angle is almost parallel to pipe axis and centre is in this region. Tests with the gray scale image were performed with darkness thresholds ranging from 10 to 140 by increments of 10. For each threshold value, pixels with gray scale value less than the threshold were marked as possible center points. Very small regions (area < 50 pixels) were also ignored since these are more likely to be stains or shadows than the actual pipe opening. Any component larger than 20% of the image area was discarded as a possible center point. Where no criteria were met, a second estimate was made based on the darkest available area of the central region. Useful in images where the original process is less effective e.g. partial water coverage images. However, this estimate is less robust than the main one as the darkest area in the frame is not always the actual center.

2.3.1 Radius Estimation

After detecting the center of the pipe, the inner radius r and the outer radius R are estimated by sampling the brightness values along 360 radial lines at each distance from the center to the edge of the image. This gives you a brightness profile outwards of the image. The interior radius r is the transition from dark to bright in the pipe opening. This is usually 5%–50% of max radius. The outer radius R is the brightness fall from bright to dark at the pipe wall. The confidence score is calculated by the strength of these brightness transitions.

If the results do not add up (e.g. if r is larger than R or the wall is too thin), fixed estimates are applied instead and confidence is set to zero. This was tested on a sample of images with known radii of 96 and 256 pixels. The algorithm detected 95 and 255 pixels, only off by 1 pixel each, with a confidence score of 0.968.

2.4 Cylindrical Unwrapping

After estimating the pipe center, the circular image is transformed into a rectangular representation by remapping pixel locations from polar coordinates to Cartesian coordinates through a linear transform. In the unwrapped result, angular position is shown through the horizontal axis in the map and radial distance through the vertical axis. The remapping is based on geometric image transforms in OpenCV, where pixels from a source image are sampled and reassigned to new positions in an output image.

During unwrapping, the algorithm samples pixels along many radial lines extending outward from the detected center. These sampled values are then rearranged into a rectangular image. Each column in the rectangular image represents a different angular direction around the pipe, and each row represents a different radial distance from the center. This process turns the circular pipe wall into a flatter surface map. The purpose of the map is not to

create a perfect physical reconstruction, but to make the visible pipe wall easier to inspect and compare across frames.

The unwrapping process utilizes two different radius values: the inner radius r , representing the inner bore boundary, and the outer radius R , representing the outer pipe wall boundary. The output image height was defined as:

$$H = R - r$$

The output image width was defined as:

$$W = 2\pi R$$

For each output pixel (u, v) , the angular coordinate was calculated as:

$$\theta = \frac{2\pi u}{W}$$

The radial coordinate was calculated as:

$$\rho = r + v$$

The corresponding original image coordinate was then calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x_0 + \rho \sin(\theta) \\ y &= y_0 + \rho \cos(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

The coordinates were then used with OpenCV’s remap function, which sampled pixels from the original image. If the mapped coordinate was outside the original image boundary, the output pixel was filled with black.

2.5 Evaluation

The method was qualitatively tested by making a visual decision of whether the center estimate was reasonable and whether the resulting unwrapped image preserved the visible wall region without large distortion. In this process lighting, shadows and visibility of the central dark region were key to produce a clear and readable map. Three main criteria of evaluation were considered. In the first case, the detected centre should visually match to the pipe axis. Second, the chosen inner and outer radii had to include the effective wall region, but not too much empty center space or background. Thirdly, the unwrapped result should maintain the wall features in an observable way that is evident for inspection. A frame was considered successful if the pipe wall was continuous and identifiable after unwrapping the frame. We flagged a frame to be weak if the center estimate was displaced by light, shadows, water or occlusion, or if the visible ring of the wall was too slim to build a useful rectangular map.

A subset of videos in the QV-Pipe database was also classified to check how many were from pipes and how many could be unwrapped properly using the proposed method. To quantify center-detection accuracy, 100 GOOD-tier frames were manually reviewed by two

separate reviewers. Frames were selected at random from the GOOD-tier set. Manual centers were calculated by viewing each frame on an enlarged scale and marking the apparent geometric center of the visible pipe opening. Both reviewers classified the center of all 100 frames using the same procedure so that reference points were consistent across the sample. The algorithm-estimated center was then compared with the manually estimated center using Euclidean pixel error:

$$e = \sqrt{(x_{\text{alg}} - x_{\text{gt}})^2 + (y_{\text{alg}} - y_{\text{gt}})^2}$$

where $(x_{\text{alg}}, y_{\text{alg}})$ is the center estimated by the algorithm and $(x_{\text{gt}}, y_{\text{gt}})$ is the manually estimated reference center. To account for different pipe sizes across frames, error was also normalized by the detected outer radius R :

$$\text{Normalized error}\% = \frac{e}{R} \times 100$$

If the error was less than or equal to 5% of the outer radius, the center estimate was considered successful. A threshold of 10% of R was also reported in order to allow for inaccuracy with manual center marking.

The two reviewers sets of manually calculated centers were compared using Cohen’s kappa to measure agreement between the two. A kappa value of 0.78 suggests that both reviewers were substantially in agreement, proving the reliability of the manual center calculations.

Processing Algorithm: Pipe Center Detection and Unwrapping

1. Input a forward-looking pipe image.
2. Convert the image from BGR to grayscale.
3. Apply a 5×5 kernel Gaussian blur to reduce background noise.
4. Restrict image bounds to the central 70% of the image’s width and height.
5. Test image components based on grayscale thresholds ranging from 10 to 140 in increments of 10:
 - (a) Mark pixels with grayscale value less than the threshold as dark.
 - (b) Remove components smaller than 50 pixels.
 - (c) Remove components larger than 20% of the image area.
 - (d) Compute mean grayscale of each remaining component.
6. Select the component with the lowest grayscale value.
7. Use the centroid of the selected component as the pipe center estimate.
8. Estimate inner radius r and outer radius R via radial intensity profiling:
 - (a) Sample mean brightness along 360 radial lines at each integer radius from center to image edge.

- (b) Compute the gradient of the brightness profile to see where it changes most.
 - (c) Find r as the radius where brightness jumps from dark to bright (the pipe opening), searching between 5% and 50% of the max radius.
 - (d) Find R as the radius where brightness drops from bright to dark (the pipe wall), searching from r outward.
 - (e) Calculate a confidence score based on how strong these brightness changes are.
 - (f) Check if the results make sense: if r is bigger than R or the wall is too thin (less than 10% of max radius), use fixed estimates instead.
9. Generate polar remapping coordinates.
 10. Use OpenCV remap to create the rectangular unwrapped map.
 11. Output the detected center, unwrapped surface map, and original image.

3 Results

The image processing system finds a center point for the pipe and generates an unwrapped rectangular panorama of the pipe wall based on the center point. The center detection system takes into account different darkness thresholds and selects the darkest zone that satisfies all requirements. If the images had the dark center area of the pipe, the program provided a usable estimate of the pipe center. The process is most accurate when the pipe wall makes a clean circle around a dark central hole. In these cases the center detection algorithm selects a point near the actual pipe center and unrolls the pipe with minimal distortion. This demonstrates the ability of the unwrapping method to transform the circular camera view into a readable surface map.

Once the center was located, the unwrapping function converted the image of the pipe from a circle to a rectangular flat view. The result was the unwrapped inner wall of the pipe with angular position on the horizontal and radial distance on the vertical axes. The unwrapped image is a flat map-like representation of the circular pipeline. This facilitates visual inspection of the side of the pipeline and reduces the challenge of interpreting curved walls of the pipeline in the original frame.

The rectangular format also enables comparisons to be made between different regions of the pipe wall. The original image shows the left, right, up and down sections of the pipe arranged around a circular center. The rectangular panorama nicely shows the pipe-wall in a readable way in the unwrapped map view. This is particularly useful for defects such as cracks, deposits or discolouration as these are seen as features on a flattened wall rather than on curved markings within a tunnel.

The method is most effective for cases where the inside of the pipe exhibits a well defined dark central region and shadows are minimized. Under these conditions, the Euclidean center error of the center-detection algorithm on a manually evaluated set of GOOD-tier frames was 1.61 pixels on average. Lighting and geometry of the pipe were a function of normalized error. In some cases the lighting condition was not uniform or there were large shadows and the algorithm went for dark regions, which were less reliable. In these cases the final

image showed some distortion, or mis-alignment. Despite the above limitations, the method successfully demonstrated the pipe-image-to-rectangular-map conversion.

Normally the process would fail for three main reasons: insufficient light, partial coverage by water and lack of circular geometry. In poorly lit frames, the darkest region did not correspond to the center of the pipe clearly. Shadows along the sides of the pipe could pull the center estimation away from the true center. In partially filled pipes, water reflections changed the appearance of the pipe, removing the circular shape. This made it harder for the algorithm to correctly identify a circular pipe. In some QV-Pipe dataset images, the camera view only showed the upper portion of the pipe rather than a full cross-section. These frames were not suitable for the current unwrapping method.

3.1 QV-Pipe Video Classification

In an analysis of how effective the unwrapping process was, 530 videos from the QV-Pipe image dataset¹³ were classified based on how well the center detection algorithm could detect the true center. Each of the videos is assigned to four different tiers based on quality. The purpose of this classification is to determine how often real sewer inspection footage is suitable for the unwrapping method. The algorithm is most accurate when the pipe appears mostly as a circle and the central opening can be cleanly identified. The four categories therefore describe not only image quality, but also whether the geometry of the frame is compatible with the current method.

Table 1: Classification of 530 QV-Pipe videos by unwrapping suitability.

Tier	Description	Count	%
GOOD	Circle detected confidently; sufficient wall visible	78	14.7
MARGINAL	Circle detected but one quality factor is weak	52	9.8
ARCH	No full circle found; only a partial bright arch	376	70.9
POOR	No circle and no arch; frame too dark or occluded	24	4.5
Total		530	100

The classification results show that the method is useful but strongly dependent on image geometry. Out of 530 videos, 78 videos, or 14.7%, were classified as GOOD. These videos had a clear circular pipe view and enough visible wall area for direct unwrapping. Another 52 videos, or 9.8%, were classified as MARGINAL. These videos could potentially be processed, but one or more quality factors were weaker, such as a thinner visible wall ring, lower contrast, or less reliable circle detection. Together, the GOOD and MARGINAL categories represent 130 videos, or 24.5% of the dataset. This suggests that about one quarter of the tested videos were reasonably compatible with the current unwrapping pipeline.

The GOOD and MARGINAL videos represent cases where the pipe walls are visible enough for cylindrical unwrapping processing to occur. The ARCH and POOR categories represent conditions where the current method is less suitable and where additional processing would be required. This helps identify frames that would not be suitable to the normal method and would require a different approach.

The r/R ratio is the ratio of the inner bore radius to the outer pipe radius. A low value means a wide visible wall annulus, meaning more of the pipe surface is in frame and can be unwrapped. Videos with $r/R < 0.65$ qualify as GOOD; those with r/R in the range 0.65–0.80 are MARGINAL; above 0.80, the visible wall ring is too thin to be useful.

The fill fraction is defined as:

$$C_f = \frac{R}{0.5 \cdot \min(h, w)}$$

Fill fraction measures how much of the image the detected circle fills. The denominator represents the maximum possible radius of a circle centered in the image, so a fill fraction of 1.0 would indicate that the detected pipe circle almost fills the smaller image dimension. A higher value means the pipe occupies more of the frame, giving more pixels of wall to inspect.

Videos with fill fraction greater than 0.40 qualify as GOOD; 0.25–0.40 is MARGINAL; below 0.25, the circle is likely a false positive. The ARCH category was assigned when no circular cross-section was found but the algorithm detected a wide bright arch across the upper part of the frame, which is characteristic of a pipe that is partially filled with water. These videos cannot be unwrapped with the current method. Of the 530 videos, 78 (14.7%) are directly suitable for unwrapping and a further 52 (9.8%) are borderline. The majority, 376 videos (70.9%), are classified as ARCH, indicating that much of the QV-Pipe database consists of footage from partially filled pipes. This result shows that many real-world sewer inspection videos do not match the ideal circular geometry assumed by the algorithm. The POOR category contained 24 videos (4.5%) where the frame was too dark, occluded, or unclear for reliable processing. This shows that the algorithm performs well in mostly visible pipes while imagery with a weak circular geometry leads to unwrapping issues.

3.2 Center-Detection Accuracy

To validate whether the center-detection step was performing accurately, we manually inspected 100 frames from the GOOD tier. The estimated apparent geometric center of the visible opening of the pipe was manually estimated for each frame and compared with the estimated center by the algorithm. Error was calculated as Euclidean pixel distance, further normalized by detected outer pipe radius R .

The average center error for the 100 GOOD-tier frames was 1.61 ± 0.83 pixels, with a median of 1.41 pixels. The mean normalized error was 4.67% of R and the median normalized error was 4.06% of R . Under the strict success threshold of normalized error less or equal to 5% of R , the algorithm was able to estimate pipe center in 67 frames of 100 giving 67% success rate. If we relax the threshold and say a normalized error of less than or equal to 10% of R then the algorithm succeeded on 97 out of 100 frames. The success rate is 97 percent.

Table 2: Quantitative center-detection accuracy on 100 GOOD-tier frames.

Metric	Result
Number of evaluated GOOD-tier frames	100
Mean Euclidean center error	1.61 px
Standard deviation	0.83 px
Median Euclidean center error	1.41 px
Mean normalized error	4.67% of R
Median normalized error	4.06% of R
Strict success threshold	Error \leq 5% of R
Strict success rate	67/100 = 67%
Lenient success threshold	Error \leq 10% of R
Lenient success rate	97/100 = 97%

These results show that the center-detection method can produce close estimates in many GOOD-tier frames, but its accuracy is still affected by shadows, uneven lighting, and ambiguity in the visible pipe opening. This supports the error analysis that center estimation is the main factor controlling the quality of the final unwrapped map.

3.3 Computational Performance

The whole pipeline takes about 27 ms to process a single frame, i.e. 36.8 frames per second processing speed. That is, faster than the 30 FPS that is needed for real time inspection so it should be OK for live use. The threshold sweep takes 55.5% of time. Threshold sweep to perform 14 times connected component analysis. This could be sped up by binary search on the thresholds, or by attempting GPU acceleration.

Table 3: Per-stage processing time averaged over 50 iterations on a 640×640 pixel image using Python 3.10, OpenCV 4.8, and NumPy 1.24 on a standard laptop (Intel i7, 16 GB RAM).

Processing Stage	Mean (ms)	Std (ms)	% of Total
Grayscale Conversion	0.38	1.18	1.4
Gaussian Blur (5×5)	0.51	0.66	1.9
Crop Central 70%	0.01	0.00	0.0
Threshold Sweep (14 thresholds)	15.10	1.01	55.5
Centroid Computation	<0.01	<0.01	0.0
Radii Estimation (r/R)	6.27	0.04	23.1
Coordinate Map Generation	2.73	0.03	10.0
OpenCV Remap	2.19	0.29	8.0
Total Pipeline	27.18	3.09	100

3.4 Sample Results from the QV-Pipe Dataset

Figs. 1–4 show sample frames of the QV-Pipe database processed by the center-detection algorithm. Each image shows the original forward-looking circular view with the detected pipe center as a blue dot, the estimated inner radius as a green circle and outer pipe boundary as a red circle. The detected inner radius r and outer radius R for each frame is shown in the top left.

Figure 1: Center detection on a QV-Pipe frame. The green circle marks the inner bore radius r ; the red circle marks the outer pipe wall R .

Figure 2: Center detection on three frames from video 27717.2 (ARCH tier) at (a) $t = 5$ s, (b) $t = 10$ s, and (c) $t = 14$ s. The pipe is partially filled with water, so the algorithm applies an arch-fit rather than a full Hough circle. The green and red circles mark r and R estimated from the visible upper arch; the thin annulus reflects the limited wall region available for unwrapping.

The sample frames demonstrate both the strengths and weaknesses of the center-detection approach. In the dry pipe example, the detected center aligns closely with the pipe axis, producing a stable basis for unwrapping. In frames with sediment or water, the algorithm can still locate the center when the circular wall remains visible. However, the lower part of the pipe may become visually inconsistent because water and sediment interrupt the normal

wall texture. These examples support the main finding that unwrapping is practical when the pipe boundary is visible, but less reliable when water, shadows, or occlusion reduce the amount of usable wall surface.

Figure 3: Stitched surface map produced from video 27717_2 (ARCH tier, starting at $t = 2$ s). The narrow strip height reflects the thin visible annulus in a partially filled pipe; the stitched map still provides a consistent view of the accessible upper wall region.

Figure 4: Unwrapped surface strip from a MARGINAL-tier video. Dark regions at the strip edge arise where the annulus exits the image boundary.

4 Discussion

The pipe images are unwrapped subject to several structural assumptions: the pipe should be circular, the water level should be low enough for the wall to be visible, and the camera should be approximately aligned with the pipe axis. The robot is not waterproof yet, so the robot-collected tests focused on empty pipes, while external datasets were used to test more varied pipe conditions. The images show visual distortion of pipe features, which is expected when unwrapping a cylinder into a rectangle.

This distortion is a tradeoff of the method. The original camera frame preserves the

tunnel-like view of the pipe, but it is difficult to inspect because the wall curves around the center. The rectangular map makes the wall easier to examine, but it cannot perfectly preserve the geometry of a curved surface. For inspection purposes, this tradeoff is acceptable because the goal is to improve visual interpretation and documentation rather than create a perfect three-dimensional reconstruction.

This paper demonstrates that unwrapping pipe imagery into a rectangular map can improve the visual interpretability of inspection images by making the pipe wall easier to examine. In the original circular camera view, defects are hard to view because they are curved around the center and appear radially distorted. The unwrapped representation makes defects easier to view by turning the circular view into a planar map, making inspection easier. The results suggest that rectangular pipe maps can serve as an intermediate representation between raw camera footage and automated defect detection.^{14, 15, 16, 17}

Instead of trying to detect cracks or deposits directly from a circular tunnel image, future systems could first unwrap the pipe wall and then analyze the rectangular map. This would make defect locations easier to describe because each point on the pipe wall would have a more consistent position in the output image. For example, a crack running along the pipe wall could be followed more easily across a rectangular map than in the original circular view.

4.1 Comparison with Prior Work

Compared with prior pipe and borehole image-processing methods, this work emphasizes a simpler and lower-cost processing system for forward-facing pipe inspection images. Deng et al.⁹ also transform forward-looking imagery into a cylindrical panorama, but their work focuses on borehole analysis rather than drainage-pipe robot imagery.

Table 4: Comparison of this work with related pipe and borehole image-processing approaches.

Method	Camera/Input Type	Approach	Uses 3D Geometry?	Main Output	Complexity
Deng et al. ⁹	Forward-facing borehole video	Cylindrical panorama generation for borehole analysis	No	Panoramic borehole view	Medium
Künzel et al. ¹⁰	Monocular fisheye pipeline imagery	Automatic sewer-pipe analysis by unrolling imagery	No	Unrolled pipe representation	Medium
Hansen et al. ¹¹	Monocular fisheye imagery	Pipe mapping using camera imagery	No, map-focused	Pipe map	High
Zhang et al. ¹²	Small-bore pipe inspection imagery	Structure-from-motion-based image unwrapping and stitching	Yes	Unwrapped and stitched pipe surface map	High
This paper	Forward-facing imagery	Center detection and polar-to-Cartesian unwrapping	No	Rectangular surface map	Low

Künzel et al.¹⁰ and Hansen et al.¹¹ use fisheye imagery for sewer-pipe analysis and pipe mapping, while the process described in this paper uses forward-facing camera images. Zhang et al.¹² use a structure-from-motion-based method that estimates camera movement across multiple frames and uses that geometric information to support image unwrapping and stitching. In contrast, the method used in this paper does not require 3D reconstruction or specialized imaging hardware and instead uses a simplified OpenCV-based center-detection and unwrapping pipeline.

However, this method depends on several assumptions about pipe geometry and inspection conditions. The pipe cross-section is expected to be circular, and the water level is assumed to be low enough for a majority of the pipe wall to be seen. In this paper, the robot was not waterproof, so experiments were done only with empty pipes. Additionally, external datasets were used to test situations with water in pipes.

The QV-Pipe results show that real-world sewer inspection footage is more complex than ideal pipe imagery. Most of the dataset was classified as ARCH rather than GOOD, which suggests that water level and partial visibility are major challenges. This does not make the method unsuccessful; instead, it defines the conditions where the method is currently most

useful. The system is best suited for dry pipes, storm drains, culverts, or pipe sections where the circular wall is mostly visible. For partially filled sewer pipes, a modified approach may be needed, such as unwrapping only the visible upper arch or combining the camera with depth sensing.

Another important aspect of the methodology used is distortion. When unwrapping a cylindrical surface onto a rectangular plane, some geometric distortion is to be expected. Distortion can become more severe if the robot camera is not at the center of the pipe, if the pipe wall is unevenly illuminated, or if the center detection inaccurately selects a center. These factors can reduce the accuracy of the final planar map and must be addressed in future refinements.

A major limitation of the current system is that it assumes the camera is approximately aligned with the pipe axis. In real inspections, the robot may tilt, rotate, or move off-center as it travels through the pipe. When this happens, the pipe opening may no longer appear as a symmetric circle. A center point can still be estimated, but the resulting unwrapping may stretch some regions and compress others. This means that the rectangular map is best understood as an interpretive inspection aid, not as a perfectly accurate geometric reconstruction.

Another limitation is that the method relies heavily on brightness differences. The center is identified largely because it is expected to be darker than the surrounding pipe wall. This works well in many forward-looking images, but it can fail when shadows, stains, water, or debris are darker than the actual center. Uneven lighting can also create false dark regions. Future versions of the algorithm could improve this by combining darkness-based center detection with edge detection, circular Hough transforms, optical flow, or machine-learning-based segmentation.

However, the approach remains a valuable low-cost image-processing tool for pipeline inspection. This demonstrates that even with simple computer-vision methods, pipeline imagery can be converted into a representation that is easier to interpret. From an engineering perspective, the value of this approach is its simplicity and low cost. The method does not require expensive sensors, specialized 3D scanning hardware, or complex training data. It uses standard image-processing tools and can operate on ordinary camera frames. This makes it practical for student-built robots, small municipalities, or early-stage inspection prototypes. Even if the method is not yet robust enough for every field condition, it demonstrates how software processing can significantly improve the usefulness of low-cost robotic inspection imagery.

Future work should focus on five specific improvements. First, center detection should be made more robust under shadows and uneven lighting. Second, the system should be tested with a waterproof robot so that partially filled pipes can be evaluated directly. Third, frame-to-frame stitching should be improved so that the final map forms a longer continuous representation of the pipe wall. Fourth, a defect-detection model could be added after unwrapping to automatically identify cracks, sediment buildup, corrosion, or blockages. Fifth, future versions of the system could make the unwrapping pipeline reliability-aware by calculating an unwrapping confidence score for each frame. This confidence score would estimate how trustworthy the rectangular surface map is likely to be before it is used for visual inspection or automated defect detection. A possible confidence score could be defined

as:

$$C = 0.30 C_w + 0.25 C_f + 0.25 C_c + 0.20 C_v$$

where C_w measures the amount of visible pipe wall, C_f measures how much of the image is occupied by the detected pipe circle, C_c measures the brightness difference between the detected center and surrounding pipe wall, and C_v measures the percentage of valid pixels in the unwrapped output. In the contrast term, μ_w represents the mean wall brightness and μ_c represents the mean center brightness. These components could be calculated as:

$$C_w = 1 - \frac{r}{R}$$

$$C_f = \frac{R}{0.5 \cdot \min(h, w)}$$

$$C_c = \frac{\mu_w - \mu_c}{\mu_w + \varepsilon}$$

$$C_v = 1 - \frac{\text{black pixels in unwrapped map}}{\text{total pixels in unwrapped map}}$$

A high confidence score would indicate that the frame has a wide visible wall region, strong center-wall contrast, and few missing regions after unwrapping. A low confidence score would warn that shadows, water, weak circular geometry, or boundary artifacts may make the unwrapped map less reliable. This would allow the system to automatically flag high-confidence frames that are suitable for defect analysis and low-confidence frames that require additional processing. These improvements would move the system from visual enhancement toward a more complete inspection and documentation tool.

4.2 Error Analysis

The most common system error was wrong identification of the centre. The program has to analyze the centre of the pipe for the unwrapping processing system. But any small error in the estimation of the center point of the pipe would distort the rectangular map output. If the center is too high, the bottom pipe will look stretched out. If the center is too far left or right, one side of the pipe can look compressed and the other side opens up. Such small errors in the estimation may induce large differences in the reliability of the map, and may bias the output in one direction.

Uneven lighting is another common source of error. If the shadows or darker parts of the pipeline are darker than the center of the pipeline, the processing system may mis-detect the center estimate. The algorithm filters dark areas in the pipe. As a process which affects the estimated centre it searches for the darkest area. Water can also cause errors by covering the center of the pipe, creating reflections and hiding the brightness patterns on the walls of the pipe line. It indicates that alternative approaches to mitigate the sources of this type of error should be adopted in the next versions of the system.

5 Conclusion

The project demonstrates that pipe inspection images acquired in a forward looking mode can be transformed into a more interpretable surface-map format using low-cost computer-vision techniques. The main contribution of this work is not only the development of a pipe inspection robot but also the design of an image-processing pipeline to convert circular views of pipes into 2D maps. Such representation enables the analysis of pipe wall and also is the basis for the future automatic defect detection.

We present a Python based image processing system that maps circular forward looking pipe images to flattened planar surface maps using polar-to-Cartesian remapping. Gray scale blob analysis was used to estimate pipe center and images were unwrapped around the central 70% of the image. The quantitative evaluation on 100 GOOD frames shows that the center-detection algorithm has a mean center error of 1.61 pixel with 97% of the frames within 10% of R . The unwrapped maps improved the interpretability of the pipe wall and the ease of inspection and investigation of the pipe wall defects. The uneven lighting and large shadows affected the estimated center conditions and therefore the process accuracy was decreased.

The tests on the QV-Pipe dataset proved that the process can be applied on real world scenarios and successfully process the selected images. Moreover, the accuracy can be reduced by the reflections and obscured areas of the pipe walls, which make it difficult to measure partially filled pipes. In conclusion, this paper demonstrates that inexpensive computer-vision techniques can be used to improve pipe inspection and help maintain water infrastructure. Using the QV-Pipe classification we showed that the method performs best on frames with visible circular pipe geometry, while the partially filled ARCH-type videos still present a major limitation.

This technique can allow the pipeline to be analyzed, which can reduce the risk and further damage of wastewater infrastructure. Future work should include better center-detection methods, waterproof testing, stitching improvements, reliability-aware confidence scoring, and a defect-classification tool to identify defects for repair. The results also clearly demonstrate the limitations of the method. It works best on a pipe wall that is mostly visible and evenly lit in a circle. Accuracy is decreased by heavy shadows and weak visibility of centre, partly filled pipes. But these limitations are useful in that they point out the next system engineering challenge. Better centre detection, waterproof testing, better stitching, confidence scoring and automated defect classification would make the method a more powerful tool for documenting and maintaining drainage infrastructure.

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